

COOPERATION OF FAMILIES AND PEDAGOGUES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

D.B. Kasimova,

teacher of the department of pre-school pedagogy and psychology, TDPU
named after Nizomi

Abstract: Cooperation between preschool education organization, family and school helps in education and upbringing of children in the preschool preparation group, development of children according to their interests.

Children's education has become important in every era. Even today, this issue is an urgent problem. We can imagine the future of our country depending on the knowledge of the growing young generation and what kind of people they will be in the future. That's why they say: "The future is in the hands of young people." Raising a child starts with the family. We call the family "small homeland". This Motherland will be the primary education school for the child. In a sense, parents are the first teachers of their children. Therefore, parents should have high moral qualities. The child of a parent who can be an example to a child with good qualities will be a well-rounded person with good character, high knowledge, and benefit to the nation in the future. Educating young people is a sacred duty of every parent to the Motherland. He should approach this duty responsibly. "Parents who want to secure their future should spend their time and effort on raising their children, who will be great people of tomorrow. The work spent on other areas may be wasted, but the work spent on the development of the child will become an inexhaustible treasure. It is no exaggeration to say that the money and time spent on the development of a child will be the basis for a prosperous life tomorrow. Preparing children of preschool age for school education is an important aspect of increasing the effectiveness of teaching. Preparation for studying at school is an important result

of preschool education organization and education given to children in the family. It is determined by the set of requirements that the school sets for the child. The unique aspect of these requirements embodies the new socio-psychological position of the student, the new tasks and duties that he must perform.

By psychologically and pedagogically preparing the children of the pre-school preparation group for school education, children's adaptation to the school environment is much easier. Through the natural adaptation of children to school conditions, it is possible to achieve educational efficiency from the first period of the school period.

The following factors are important in the general preparation of children for school education:

- Moral and spiritual readiness of the child to study at school;
- Mental readiness of the child to study at school;
- Physical readiness of a preschool child to study at school.

The moral and moral preparation of the child to study at school prepares the ground for the child's adaptation to school conditions, responsible fulfillment of his obligations, and the formation of his moral attitude towards teachers and students. Spiritual and moral preparation is inextricably linked with mental and physical preparation of my child. The preschool education organization's system of working with the family should have a clear goal and content. Regarding cooperation with parents, it is necessary to first analyze the results of achievements and experiences, show the positive aspects of the child, and then gradually eliminate the negative situations in their behavior, and make efforts to increase their interest in the environment. So, what should be the preparation of a child of preschool age? an important question arises.

In order to ensure the comprehensive development of the child, the work of the preschool education organization in cooperation with parents is also considered important.

In this:

- taking into account the opinions of parents regarding the organization of preschool education;
- educating parents on issues of early development;
- involving parents to actively participate in the educational process;
- support for parents' initiatives to participate in the life of the organization.

Abu Ali ibn Sina wrote in his book "The Laws of Medicine": "The educator's focus is on improving the child's character, on making the child's strong anger, fear, harsh nature alien to him, on what the child wants and strives for. and it is necessary to focus on not doing what he does not like in front of him. With this, two-sided benefits are achieved: firstly, a strong positive character is formed in the child from his early childhood; secondly, such development has a positive effect on the child's physical development After all, anger is a powerful motivator, a heavy nature is exhausting, and laziness reduces the vital forces.

From time immemorial, our forefathers attached great importance to the young generation growing up to be well-behaved, polite, knowledgeable, capable children. If a child grows up to be incompetent, not only the parents will suffer, but also the country, society, and state. That is why family education has important political significance. A child with a strong imagination receives his first upbringing in the family. "It is necessary to start education from the day of birth, to strengthen our body, to clarify our mind"

It is not for nothing that there are many myths, legends, proverbs and tales about raising a child among our people. Wise people say that a child should be educated from the mother's womb. When a child is well-educated, he can become a perfect scholar and a perfect person.

In conclusion, parents are role models for children and ideal people for them. Children take their parents' views as an example. Even according to scientific evidence, when the child is growing in the mother's womb, what kind of emotion

does the mother have (being sad, happy, crying, hating a person), this is also passed from mother to child during pregnancy. as long as Therefore, it is necessary to start helping the mother to raise her child during pregnancy. It is important for parents to give their children basic education and upbringing at home in addition to the school environment, to open the way for them to discover a new world. for the child's development, both the teacher and the parents, and even the child himself, must make an effort. Only then will there be growth and results. The role of parents in raising a child is incomparable. Parents should pay attention to their child's upbringing and learning. In order for society to progress, education must be effective. For effective upbringing, parents should be knowledgeable. Our children will develop the country with knowledge.

Books:

1. .Касимова, Д. Б. (2022). ОСНОВНЫЕ ПРИНЦИПЫ СОЗДАНИЯ ПРЕДМЕТНО-РАЗВИВАЮЩЕЙ СРЕДЫ. *International Academic Research Journal Impact Factor 7.4*, 1(6), 244-248.
2. Bakhodirovna, K. D. (2022). Management of the Plot-Role-Playing Games of Preschool Children in the Conditions of Pre-School Education. *Spanish Journal of Society and Sustainability*, 3, 9-11.
3. Касимова, Д. Б. (2022, November). СОВРЕМЕННЫЙ ПОДХОД И НОВЕЙШИЕ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ ТРЕБОВАНИЯ К СЮЖЕТНО-РОЛЕВЫМ ИГРАМ ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE" THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS"* (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 108-112).
4. Касимова, Д. Б. (2022). СПЕЦИФИЧЕСКИЕ МОТИВЫ, ПРИСУЩИЕ СЮЖЕТНО-РОЛЕВЫМ ИГРАМ ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ. *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal*, 1(6), 239-243.
5. Tairovna, Z. N. (2022). The Role of Didactic Tools in the Mathematical Development of Children. *Spanish Journal of Society and Sustainability*, 3, 39-40.

6. Jurayeva, N. T. (2022, November). Methods of implementation and mechanisms of implementation of the norms of international law. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE" THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS"* (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 113-120).

7. Juraeva, N. T. (2022). Organization of the educational process in preschool educational organizations. *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal*, 1(6), 244-251.

8. [D.M.Maxmudova Sposoby zainteresovat doskolnikov chteniem.](#)// international scientific and practical conference" the time of scientific 2022y

9. D.M.Maxmudova [Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni ertaklar vositasida kitobxonlikka tayyorlashning pedagogik mexanizmlari](#)// Zamonaviy dunyoda pedagogika va psixologiya: Nazariy va amaliy izlanishlar 112-115b. 2022y